

Design and Development of Automated Guided Vehicles for Active Learning in Material Handling Management for Smart Manufacturing Operation

Yasiru Shikshitha Malshan Benaragama, Pisut Koomsap

Department of Industrial Systems Engineering, Asian Institute of Technology, Pathumthani, Thailand

Email: fluxes94@gmail.com, pisut@ait.asia

Abstract

Automated guided vehicles (AGVs) have become a preferred material handling system commonly seen for logistics in a manufacturing facility in the modern days when flexibility is critical in smart manufacturing for offering a variety of low volume products to serve individual demands. Accessibility to AGVs, however, is very limited in school due to their commercially high costs, complexity, and restrictions imposed by the manufacturers in alterations. This paper presents the design and development of a fleet of in-house AGVs to support the active learning of students with hands-on experience in the material handling management in smart manufacturing. The AGVs were designed and built in a modular manner with open-source, off the shelf parts that can be swapped, altered, and changed as necessary to allow access to almost all aspects of the AGV, such as access to inertial measurements of bearing, velocity and acceleration, motor readings of speed and power consumption, live camera feed for image processing, various proximity readings, magnetic line following output and many more features in order to give sufficient resources for the students to experiment on. They also allow students to execute their algorithms on the AGVs to get hands-on experience in AGV fleet management and navigation.

Keywords: AGVs, Material Handling Management, smart manufacturing, hands-on experience

1 Introduction

As the industries move towards the Industry 4.0 era, syllabi related to outdated technology that is being taught to engineering students becomes irrelevant (R.Toto & Nguyen, 2009). The contents taught for the next generation of engineers should be up to date so that they will be ready with the knowledge they ought to have when they enter industries. To do this, educational institutes should have syllabi and infrastructure to meet these demands. Educational institutes have experimented on integrating industrial engineering courses with real-world scenarios to improve students' IT skills and improve their problem-solving abilities (Frank et al, 2003). The relationship between active learning and creation of innovative minds are explored and proven in recent studies in Japanese universities (Ito and Kawazoe, 2015). The forward thinkers in Industrial Systems Engineering at Asian Institute of Technology, always strive towards the development of technologies to satisfy the requirements for industries of tomorrow. The importance of having such support systems which gives students a chance of learning autonomously (Gonzalez et al, 2016) are quite obvious. The lecturers at AIT are teaching the knowledge of the future so that the students are one step ahead once they enter industries. To help in this endeavour, Industrial Systems Engineering (ISE) has developed a Smart Future Learning Factory to support the student learning in an Erasmus+ Curriculum development of Masters Degree program in Industrial Engineering for Thailand Sustainable Smart Industry (MSIE 4.0), which was funded by the European Commission.

The Smart Learning Future Factory upon completion will have many resources which can be used to educate students on subjects related to the industry. Such a Smart Learning Future Factory has the capacity to train engineering students by giving them a practical understanding about Industry 4.0 (Learning factory modules). The impact of these Smart Factories has on students and the positive outcomes they show can be seen from Smart Factories already established in universities (Neser, Simonsa and Abéa, 2017). When considering the Smart Factory at AIT, among the many resources the Smart Factory will possess, one asset that is already operational and implemented in the Smart Factory is the Material Handling System built specifically for the Smart Factory.

This Material Handling System consists of 5 prototype Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs). Among the many services expected out of these assets, the AGVs will act as the material handling units between the workstations established in the Smart Factory, and these AGVs will also be a platform from which students can gather knowledge related to industrial engineering, further proving the use of robots in teaching students on developing problem solving skills among many other advantages (Flowers & Gossett, 2002). The AGVs also acts as an important asset in the Smart Factory by representing a physical system integrated with emerging technologies such as IOT (Internet of Things) and cloud computing, all key components of a Smart Factory (Chen et al, 2018).

From the information provided above, the importance of active learning for students in a classroom environment is clear. This paper provides an answer on approaching an effective active learning environment; by having AGV mobile units as a platform from which the students gain hands-on experience in engineering-related subjects. Section 2 will discuss initial design and development phase of the AGVs followed by secondary aspects such as communication architecture and electronics assembly. Section 3 discuss how these AGVs are used in an active learning environment followed by concluding in section 5.

2 AGV development

The AGVs, all software and hardware including the PCBs were designed and developed by the first author for his Master Thesis dissertation. The AGVs were designed keeping in mind the primary goal, a platform from which the students get hands-on experience of technology. Research carried out had proven that active learning where the students learn by interacting with their environment as opposed to education received by lectures, is more effective in knowledge gathering (Linder et al, 2001). This influenced the design choices of the prototype AGVs. Also, the requirements an AGV must have for an Industry 4.0 factory was researched upon (L. Cavanini et al, 2018). Figure 1 shows the CAD design of the AGVs with all the major components pointed out. The AGVs were to be lightweight for the students to easily handle, but strong enough to carry the specified weight of the payload effortlessly. The structural framework should be able to be altered, upgraded and external devices should be able to be mounted to the framework without much hassle. Hence, the entire structural framework was built from standard aluminium profile bars, which meets all of the above demands. The outer body was made by acrylic plastic and offered easy access to internal components.

Figure 1: The CAD design of the AGV. The primary components are marked in the figure.

Adhering to the requirements of the AGV to be used as a learning platform and considering the required payload capacity, the required dimensions and other relevant data, the CAD drawing was done. The AGV was built in a

modular fashion so that further improvements can be done by future student who will work on it. The two rails on top offers the capability of mounting accessories such as the material handling unit built for the AGV, or a robotic arm, or any other equipment. Special characteristics of the design is given below.

- Lightweight aluminium frame.
- Mecanum wheels which offer more flexibility in navigation.
- Industrial magnetic line following sensor.
- Raspberry-Pi computer with onboard camera and Wi-Fi connectivity.
- 14 proximity sensors which are used in collision avoidance.
- 22 Ah 24-volt LiPo battery for long lasting operation from a single charge.
- 5.5 -inch LED touchscreen
- Digital gyroscope to keep track of the bearing of the AGV during free navigation.

The aluminium framework was chosen for its excellent rigidity while being light weight. The outer body was made using acrylic for aesthetics.

The next step in the development phase was to design the electronics of the AGVs. A printed circuit board was designed specially for the AGVs. By doing this, all the electronics of the AGV was securely fastened to one circuit board which will avoid unnecessary wiring being done on AGVs.

Beside connecting different peripherals together, the PCB offered many functions to the AGV operation. Among its many roles, the board acted as the power distribution panel for the motors and the peripherals. The control panel provided the user the possibility of interacting with the AGV. the lifter assembly provided power and control over the peripherals that will be connector to the material handling unit. The front panel distributed power and received information from the proximity sensors connected in front.

3 Communication protocols used

The AGV can be connected via Wi-Fi to an existing Local Area Network (LAN) for a successful data transfer to and from the AGV. No specially built communication devices are needed in order to establish a stable connection. The students use the inbuilt Wi-Fi of the Raspberry-Pi computer to form a stable TCP connection with the computer. Since Raspberry-Pi is, after all, a computer, students have the freedom to choose the mode of communication, even if they opt to switch to Bluetooth. Once everything is in order, the AGVs will be deployed from its docking station (figure 2) and carry out the orders sent to it.

Figure 2: The AGVs at their docking station, ready to execute commands.

4 Active learning based on the developed AGVs

The exposure of active learning in a Smart Learning Future Factory received by Industrial Engineering students will not be limited to knowledge gathered in studies specific to industrial engineering. The many different fields of engineering the students will be exposed to includes mechanical engineering, electrical engineering, electronic engineering, computer science, etc. The students will have experience in taking critical decisions, take responsibilities, meet demands and deadlines, and many more life-essential skills.

To help students in achieving these skills, the AGVs will act as a learning platform, that can be used to experiment on managing a Smart Factory equipped with flexible manufacturing and material handling systems. Students can learn to control AGVs to support the collaborative manufacturing processes happening in the factory. The AGVs with modular architecture offer flexibility in modifications and improvements using plug in components. Students can also learn about programming, experiment on coding and try new ideas.

3.1 Active Learning in Industrial Engineering

IE students require real world experience in managing resources in a factory. The AGVs are developed for students to control in a factory environment and to learn about production management. The primary function of the AGV are to act as material handling units. Students who wish to learn on task scheduling, inventory management, supply chain management and other related studies now has the chance of experimenting these aspects in real life. In-process items in the Smart Factory will be carried between the modular workstations, and the warehouse in which the items are stored. Task scheduling in between workstations, the AGVs and all other assets can be done so that the students gather knowledge on maintaining a Smart Factory.

The existing system in the Smart Factory which controls the AGVs has the capability of commanding AGVs to navigate in between workstations according to the user input. Students may use this knowledge, and take the status of the workstations into consideration and experiment on scheduling pick up and delivery and all related events.

3.2 Active learning of Electronics by IE students

Dealing with electronic components will be an essential skill for the students in the near future, due to the multi-disciplinary requirements in an Industry 4.0 era. The electronics of the AGV used up off the shelf components, easily accessible for repairs and upgrades. The reason to use these common electronics components is because of the familiarity most engineering students already have with them. Open source microcontrollers such as Arduino and ESP32 was used in the electronics assembly. A printed circuit board (PCB) was specially designed for the AGVs in order to effortlessly mount these accessories. Overall, the important components connected to the PCB was the Arduino Microcontrollers, the digital Gyroscope sensor, the industrial grade magnetic line following sensor and the Raspberry-Pi computer.

Due to this modular nature of the electronics in the AGV, repairs and upgrades can easily be carried out on the units. Students may experiment on different microcontrollers, different development boards and more powerful microprocessors if they choose to. This will increase the capabilities of the AGVs much more than what it is now. One of the most important electronic components in the AGV is the digital gyroscope. It constantly measures the current bearing of the AGV in order to precisely navigate when it is in free ranging mode. Students may experiment on different gyroscope modules available in the market and modify the AGV thanks to the modular nature of the electronics.

By involving in work related to electronics, industrial engineering students gets an idea on the basics of the electronics that they may encounter in industries. The AGVs provide a platform from which the students can get an experience of dealing with problems related to electronics, how to solve these problems, and how to improve existing electronics. These skills will be vital to the students as industrial engineers.

3.3 Active Learning in Computer Science by IE students

Industrial engineering students who are keen on developing their skills on programming languages will have the opportunity to access all of the source codes in the AGV. Low level programming languages such as C++ are used in the microcontrollers, which are responsible in the localized control of the AGV, its motor speed, the

degree of rotation, the proximity sensor readings, the data from the magnetic sensor, etc. The students will have a chance of experimenting with the internal functionality of the AGV by studying how the localized operations occur. They will get an understanding on how the information received from the Raspberry-Pi computer is decrypted, analysed and acted upon. They will have a chance to gather all the data from the AGV's many sensors (magnetic guide sensor, proximity sensors, the digital Gyroscope, Magnetometer and Accelerometer, the current sensors of all the motors, etc.) and make rational decisions on how to act upon all the gathered data. Students may use this vital information to make the AGVs more intelligent. For instance, the algorithm that runs in the AGVs (at the time of writing this report) detects collisions it encounters by the sudden spikes in accelerometer data (given that the proximity sensors missed the obstacle), and then take precautionary measures to mitigate the issue. But students can use the readings of yaw, pitch and roll to make assessments of sudden changes in orientation, read the current consumption of the motors to detect abnormal current drawn from the motors during a collision as methods of detecting collisions. They may even use a combination of these sensory reading to come to a more validated decision. This is just one example which shows how students may develop the AGV units further.

The communication links was established using JavaScript coding language, which is a high-level programming language, in order to have a stable, robust and a reliable Wi-Fi connection, that will regain a broken link automatically, if such a thing was to occur. In default, the algorithms that runs in both the Raspberry-Pi and the main control computer will link the AGV to the main control computer automatically. The students will have the opportunity to study the source code, and do alterations in the hope of increasing the performance of the functionality.

One other aspect of the AGV open for students to develop is related to machine vision. The AGV comes with an onboard camera attached to the Raspberry-Pi onboard computer which has the potential to perform machine vision and act as a method for localization. By doing this, the AGVs can be made as fully free ranging robots, with the ability to locate and navigate themselves and even to detect and avoid obstacles in its path, all done with the power of machine vision.

As the industry move towards Industry 4.0 era, it will be a basic requirement for industrial engineers to have computer programming skills, and knowledge on how computer networking is done, among many other requirements. Knowledge on these studies are seldom taught in a classroom environment since these are the knowledge and experiences gained from an active learning environment.

3.4 Active learning in AGV Fleet management and problem solving by IE students

The Master Thesis research of the first author was to design and develop a fleet management system that was developed specially for the 5 prototype AGVs. By using the built hardware and the built stable communication links, the decentralized AGV fleet management system is operational and implemented (at the time of writing this report) to the Smart Factory. The algorithm developed for the fleet management algorithm enabled the AGVs to navigate autonomously according to the requests made by the modular workstations located within the Smart Factory. For a typical operation where a workstation (source workstation) has an in-process item to be delivered to destination workstation, the most suitable AGV will travel to the source workstation, pick up the item, and then travel to the destination workstation to deliver the item.

Industrial engineering students who are keen on developing the existing fleet management algorithm, or students who wish to implement their own fleet management algorithm can access the source code related to the existing system, learn from it, and improve it. Since the source codes are not protected by proprietary laws, like the ones seen on commercial machinery, the students have total accessibility to the raw codes. Users however should be mindful about the operation of the AGVs and take necessary precautions not to harm themselves, others or the AGV units, when testing new source codes.

The infrastructure built to the Smart Factory for AGV navigation (figure 3) consists of areas of free ranging navigation and specific areas (special in the vicinity of the workstations) of fixed path navigation. Even though the AGVs switches between fixed path and free ranging navigation automatically, students may experiment on different approaches to navigational routines, whether fixed path or free ranging navigation, and come up with much better and more efficient navigational protocols.

Figure 3: The layout of the Smart Learning Future Factory. The fixed path navigation routes for the AGVs are shown in yellow lines. The open space in the middle allows flexible AGV navigation.

The students have the ability to use a single AGV or multiple AGVs at a time for them to learn on how material handling units function in a factory. They can research on effective path planning and time scheduling in pick up and delivery, do continuous improvement in AGV fleet management and all related algorithms in order to get the maximum efficiency in material handling in the smart factory. The students may work as teams or individually and lecturers can assess the results and outcomes of the students in an active learning environment.

5 Conclusion

The Masters Degree program in Industrial Engineering for Thailand Sustainable Smart Industry (MSIE 4.0), at the Asian Institute of Technology, is oriented towards a hands-on student learning experience, along with the standard teaching methods. This is the reason for the development of the Smart Future Learning Factory, which was funded by the Erasmus+ curriculum development program by the European Union. One key aspect of the Smart Factory is the material handling system specially developed for the Factory. This material handling system consists of five prototype AGVs and the infrastructure built for its navigation. This paper discussed the potential applications of these robots not merely as a material handling unit, but also as a student learning platform with the capability of providing knowledge to industrial engineering students in so many different fields of engineering, including industrial engineering, mechanical engineering, computer science and information and communication studies.

One important aspect of the AGVs when compared with the works available in the literature is the wide range of use these robotic platforms offer when viewed from an academic point of view. The AGVs offer enormous flexibility in improving almost every aspect of it; electronics, mechanical, communication etc. The students get to interact and experiment their research and development on a real physical system. These units offer no limitations seen by industrial robots, where the accessibility to the core operations are severely limited thanks to the company policies. The prototype AGVs offer the same functionality as industrial grade AGVs at a much lower price with much more room for further development.

These AGVs developed for the Smart Factory will help students learn needed knowledge for the Industry 4.0 era by the hands-on experience gained through research and experimentation, and by doing so, produce talented industrial engineers who are experienced in many different fields of engineering, for the future of industry.

Acknowledgements

This work is the outcome of project "Curriculum Development of Master's Degree Program in Industrial Engineering for Thailand Sustainable Smart Industry (MSIE 4.0)" that has been funded with support from the European Commission (Project Number: 586137-EPP-1-2017-1-TH-EPPKA2-CBHE-JP). This publication reflects the views only of the authors, and the Commission cannot be held responsible for any use which may be made of the information contained therein.

6 References

- Cavanini, L et al., "A Preliminary Study of a Cyber Physical System for Industry 4.0: Modelling and Co-Simulation of an AGV for Smart Factories," 2018 Workshop on Metrology for Industry 4.0 and IoT, Brescia, 2018, pp. 169-174, doi: 10.1109/METROI4.2018.8428334.
- Chen ,B., Wan ,J., Shu, L., Li, P., Mukherjee, M. and Yin, B., "Smart Factory of Industry 4.0: Key Technologies, Application Case, and Challenges," in IEEE Access, vol. 6, pp. 6505-6519, 2018, doi: 10.1109/ACCESS.2017.2783682.
- Flowers, T. R., and Gossett, K. A., 2002. Teaching problem solving, computing, and information technology with robots. *J. Comput. Sci. Coll.* 17, 6 (May 2002), 45–55.
- González-González, C. S., Moreno, L., Popescu, B., Lotero, Y. and Vargas, R., "Intelligent systems to support the active self-learning in industrial automation," 2016 IEEE Global Engineering Education Conference (EDUCON), Abu Dhabi, 2016, pp. 1149-1154, doi: 10.1109/EDUCON.2016.7474700.
- Ito, H. and Kawazoe, N., 2015. Active Learning for Creating Innovators: Employability Skills beyond Industrial Needs. *International Journal of Higher Education*, 4(2).
- Linder, S. P., Nestruck, B. E., Mulders, S., and Lavelle, C. L., 2001. Facilitating active learning with inexpensive mobile robots. *J. Comput. Sci. Coll.* 16, 4 (2001), 21–33.
- Neser, S., Simonsa, S. and Abéa, P., 2017. Learning in the AutFab – the fully automated Industrie 4.0 learning factory of the University of Applied Sciences Darmstadt. *Procedia Manufacturing*, 9, pp.81-88.
- Peters, Frank; Jackman, John K.; Ryan, Sarah M.; and Olafsson, Sigurdur, "An Active Learning Environment in an Integrated IndustrialEngineering Curriculum" (2003). *Industrial and Manufacturing Systems Engineering Conference Proceedings and Posters*. 77
- Toto, R. and Nguyen, H., "Flipping the Work Design in an industrial engineering course," 2009 39th IEEE Frontiers in Education Conference, San Antonio, TX, 2009, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/FIE.2009.5350529.